

Mastering Apply: From Matrices to Multidimensional Neuroimaging Data

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In my [first apply post](#), I briefly showed `apply()` converting columns to character, but I glossed over what makes `apply()` special. Here's the thing: `apply()` is actually quite different from `sapply()` and `mapply()`. While those work on lists and vectors, `apply()` is designed specifically for matrices and arrays.

Pattern recognition

Use `apply()` when you have:

- Matrix or array data (not `data.frame` - use `dplyr` for those)
- Need to collapse one or more dimensions by applying a function
- Want to apply the same operation across rows, columns, or higher dimensions
- Working with multidimensional scientific data (neuroimaging, climate models, genomics, etc.)

The syntax is always: `apply(X, MARGIN, FUN, ...)`

Where: - `X` is your matrix or array - `MARGIN` specifies which dimension(s) to preserve (1 = rows, 2 = columns, 3+ = higher dimensions) - `FUN` is the function to apply - `...` are additional arguments passed to `FUN`

Think of `MARGIN` as telling R “keep these dimensions, collapse everything else.” That’s where the magic happens.

I’m going to be honest - when I first encountered `apply()`, the `MARGIN` parameter confused the heck out of me. “Why do I need to specify margins? What does that even mean?” But once it clicked, I realized how powerful this function is for working with structured data. Understanding `apply()` properly will save you from writing many unnecessary loops when working with matrix-like data.

The MARGIN parameter explained

The MARGIN parameter tells `apply()` which dimension to “collapse” by applying your function. I know that sounds abstract, so let me show you what I mean. It’s much easier to understand with examples than with explanations.

Note:

The MARGIN parameter can be either numeric (e.g., 1 for rows, 2 for columns) or a character vector specifying the *names* of the dimensions (if your array or matrix has named dimensions). For example, if your array has `dimnames`, you can use `MARGIN = "Subject"` instead of its numeric index.

Let’s start with a simple matrix - just numbers arranged in rows and columns:

```
# Create a 4x3 matrix (4 rows, 3 columns)
test_matrix <- matrix(1:12, nrow = 4, ncol = 3)
test_matrix
```

```
      [,1] [,2] [,3]
[1,]    1    5    9
[2,]    2    6   10
[3,]    3    7   11
[4,]    4    8   12
```

We’ve got a matrix with 4 rows and 3 columns. Each row could represent a different observation, and each column could be a different variable. Now, let’s see what happens when we apply `sum()` across different margins:

```
# MARGIN = 1: apply across rows (each row becomes one value)
apply(test_matrix, MARGIN = 1, FUN = sum)
```

```
[1] 15 18 21 24
```

Notice what happened? We got 4 values - one for each row. `MARGIN = 1` means “for each row, apply the function and give me one result.” So R took each row, summed up all the values in that row, and gave us back a vector of 4 sums.

Now let’s try the other direction:

```
# MARGIN = 2: apply across columns (each column becomes one value)
apply(test_matrix, MARGIN = 2, FUN = sum)
```

```
[1] 10 26 42
```

This time we got 3 values - one for each column! `MARGIN = 2` means “for each column, apply the function and give me one result.”

Here’s how I think about it: - `MARGIN = 1`: “Process each row” → Number of rows determines output length - `MARGIN = 2`: “Process each column” → Number of columns determines output length

The margin you specify is the dimension that gets *preserved* in your output. Everything else gets collapsed by your function.

Real-world example: Student grades

Okay, let’s move beyond toy examples. Imagine Each row is a student, each column is an assignment. This is actually a really common data structure in many fields - observations in rows, variables in columns.

```
# Rows = students, Columns = assignments
# styler: off
grades <- matrix(
  c(
    85, 92, 78, 88, # Student 1
    90, 85, 95, 87, # Student 2
    78, 83, 80, 85, # Student 3
    95, 88, 92, 90, # Student 4
    82, 79, 84, 81  # Student 5
  ),
  nrow = 5,
  byrow = TRUE
)

colnames(grades) <- c("Quiz1", "Quiz2", "Midterm", "Final")
rownames(grades) <- paste("Student", 1:5)
grades
```

	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
Student 1	85	92	78	88
Student 2	90	85	95	87
Student 3	78	83	80	85
Student 4	95	88	92	90
Student 5	82	79	84	81

Now we can easily answer questions like “What’s each student’s average?” and “Which assignment was hardest?”

To get each student’s average, we want to work across columns for each row (sum up all their assignments and divide by the number of assignments):

```
# Student averages (across columns for each row)
student_averages <- apply(grades, MARGIN = 1, FUN = mean)
student_averages
```

```
Student 1 Student 2 Student 3 Student 4 Student 5
      85.75      89.25      81.50      91.25      81.50
```

See how clean that is? No loops, no indexing nightmares. Just “hey R, for each student (row), calculate the mean.” If you want to use the names of the dimensions instead of the numbers, you will need to give the dimensions names first. We have so far given each column and each row a name, but we haven’t named the row and column themselves. This is done by setting the `dimnames` attribute of the matrix:

```
dimnames(grades)
```

```
[[1]]
[1] "Student 1" "Student 2" "Student 3" "Student 4" "Student 5"
```

```
[[2]]
[1] "Quiz1" "Quiz2" "Midterm" "Final"
```

```
dimnames(grades) <- list(
  Student = rownames(grades),
  Assignment = colnames(grades)
)
dimnames(grades)
```

```
$Student
[1] "Student 1" "Student 2" "Student 3" "Student 4" "Student 5"
```

```
$Assignment
[1] "Quiz1" "Quiz2" "Midterm" "Final"
```

```
apply(grades, MARGIN = "Student", FUN = mean)
```

```
Student 1 Student 2 Student 3 Student 4 Student 5
      85.75      89.25      81.50      91.25      81.50
```

What about assignment difficulty? We can look at the average score for each assignment by working down the columns:

```
# Assignment averages (across rows for each column)
assignment_averages <- apply(grades, MARGIN = 2, FUN = mean)
assignment_averages
```

```
Quiz1 Quiz2 Midterm Final
  86.0  85.4  85.8   86.2
```

Looks like Quiz 2 was the toughest (or maybe everyone was hungover that week?). The midterm was actually easier than the quizzes on average.

This is so much cleaner than writing loops! Compare this to what you'd have to do with a for loop - you'd need to initialize empty vectors, loop through indices, store results... it's just messy.

Beyond mean: useful functions for apply

The function you pass to `apply()` can be anything that makes sense for your data. Let's explore some other common operations you might want to do with gradebook data.

Want to know how consistent each student's performance is? Standard deviation tells you that:

```
# Standard deviation for each student (higher = more variable)
apply(grades, 1, sd)
```

```
Student 1 Student 2 Student 3 Student 4 Student 5
  5.909033  4.349329  3.109126  2.986079  2.081666
```

Student 1 has the highest variability - maybe they're really good at some things and struggle with others? Student 4 is super consistent.

What about the range of scores for each assignment?

```
# Range (min to max) for each assignment
apply(grades, 2, range)
```

```
      Assignment
      Quiz1 Quiz2 Midterm Final
[1,]    78    79     78    81
[2,]    95    92     95    90
```

This gives us a matrix where the first row is minimums and second row is maximums for each assignment. Here's a fun one - which assignment was each student's worst?

```
apply(grades, 1, which.min)
```

```
Student 1 Student 2 Student 3 Student 4 Student 5
      3         2         1         2         2
```

These are column indices. We can make this more readable by looking up the actual assignment names:

```
# Get the assignment names instead of indices
colnames(grades)[apply(grades, 1, which.min)]
```

```
[1] "Midterm" "Quiz2"  "Quiz1"  "Quiz2"  "Quiz2"
```

Now that's informative! Three students struggled most with Quiz2.

Custom functions with apply

You're not limited to built-in functions. You can pass your own functions too, which is where things get really powerful.

Let's say we want to calculate letter grades based on each student's average. We need a function that takes a vector of scores, calculates the mean, and returns a letter:

```

get_letter_grade <- function(scores) {
  avg <- mean(scores)
  if (avg >= 90) {
    return("A")
  }
  if (avg >= 80) {
    return("B")
  }
  if (avg >= 70) {
    return("C")
  }
  if (avg >= 60) {
    return("D")
  }
  return("F")
}

# Letter grade for each student
apply(grades, 1, get_letter_grade)

```

```

Student 1 Student 2 Student 3 Student 4 Student 5
      "B"      "B"      "B"      "A"      "B"

```

One A and 4 B's, impressive!

Here's something more interesting - let's figure out if students are improving over time. We can calculate a simple correlation between time (assignment order) and scores:

```

calculate_trend <- function(scores) {
  # Simple linear trend (positive = improving, negative = declining)
  x <- seq_along(scores)
  trend <- cor(x, scores)
  return(trend)
}

# Trend for each student (are they improving over time?)
trends <- apply(grades, 1, calculate_trend)
trends

```

```

      Student 1      Student 2      Student 3      Student 4      Student 5
-0.10923907  0.02968261  0.74740932 -0.47557147  0.12403473

```

Student 3 has the strongest positive trend (0.7474093) - they started rough but ended strong! Good for them. Student 4 has a negative trend (-0.4755715) - started great but faded. Maybe they need some extra help?

The cool thing about custom functions is you can make them as complex as you need. Statistical tests, transformations, summarizations - whatever makes sense for your analysis.

Working with 3D arrays

Now we're getting into territory where `apply()` really starts to shine. Let's say instead of one class, you're teaching multiple sections. Or maybe you're running a longitudinal study with multiple measurement occasions. Suddenly you need a third dimension.

Let me simulate something realistic: test scores for 5 students across 4 assignments in 3 different classes:

```
# 3D array: 5 students × 4 assignments × 3 classes
set.seed(42)
scores_3d <- array(
  round(rnorm(60, mean = 85, sd = 10)),
  dim = c(5, 4, 3),
  dimnames = list(
    Student = paste("S", 1:5, sep = ""),
    Assignment = c("Quiz1", "Quiz2", "Midterm", "Final"),
    Class = c("Math", "Science", "English")
  )
)

# Look at the whole structure
scores_3d
```

```
, , Class = Math
```

	Assignment			
Student	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
S1	99	84	98	91
S2	79	100	108	82
S3	89	84	71	58
S4	91	105	82	61
S5	89	84	84	98

```
, , Class = Science
```

	Assignment			
Student	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
S1	82	81	90	68
S2	67	82	92	77
S3	83	67	95	76
S4	97	90	79	61
S5	104	79	90	85

, , Class = English

	Assignment			
Student	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
S1	87	89	88	88
S2	81	77	77	92
S3	93	99	101	86
S4	78	81	91	55
S5	71	92	86	88

This is now a 3-dimensional array. Think of it like a cube of numbers. We can slice it to look at just one class:

```
# Just the Math class
scores_3d[, , "Math"]
```

	Assignment			
Student	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
S1	99	84	98	91
S2	79	100	108	82
S3	89	84	71	58
S4	91	105	82	61
S5	89	84	84	98

Now, with `apply()`, we can answer all sorts of questions by specifying which dimensions to collapse.

Want each student's overall average across all assignments and all classes? We keep dimension 1 (students) and collapse dimensions 2 (assignments) and 3 (classes):

```
# Student averages across all assignments and classes
# Keep dimension 1, collapse dimensions 2 and 3
apply(scores_3d, MARGIN = "Student", FUN = mean)
```

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
	87.08333	84.50000	83.50000	80.91667	87.50000

What if we want to know which assignments are hardest on average, regardless of student or class? Keep dimension 2 (assignments), collapse dimensions 1 (students) and 3 (classes):

```
# Assignment difficulty across all students and classes
# Keep dimension 2, collapse dimensions 1 and 3
apply(scores_3d, MARGIN = "Assignment", FUN = mean)
```

	Quiz1	Quiz2	Midterm	Final
	86.00000	86.26667	88.80000	77.73333

Or we could see which class has the highest average:

```
# Class averages across all students and assignments
# Keep dimension 3, collapse dimensions 1 and 2
apply(scores_3d, MARGIN = "Class", FUN = mean)
```

	Math	Science	English
	86.85	82.25	85.00

Here's where it gets really cool - you can specify *multiple* margins to keep. Say we want each student's average in each class (but collapsed across assignments):

```
# Average for each student in each class
# Keep dimensions 1 and 3, collapse dimension 2 (assignments)
apply(scores_3d, MARGIN = c(1, 3), FUN = mean)
```

	Class		
Student	Math	Science	English
S1	93.00	80.25	88.00
S2	92.25	79.50	81.75
S3	75.50	80.25	94.75
S4	84.75	81.75	76.25
S5	88.75	89.50	84.25

Now we get a matrix: rows are students, columns are classes, values are averages. This is super useful for generating summary tables.

The key insight is that `MARGIN` tells you what dimensions you want to *preserve* in your output. Everything else gets fed to your function.

Real neuroimaging example: fMRI data

Alright, this is where I get excited. This is where `apply()` goes from “handy” to “absolutely essential.”

Neuroimaging data is inherently multidimensional. Most of us are aware that digital images are made of lots and lots of pixels — tiny squares, each with a single value. Together, all these pixels form a complete 2D image.

When we record brain activity using MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) — a technique for taking detailed pictures of the inside of the body, especially the brain—the concept is similar, but in three dimensions. Instead of a pixel, we record a tiny cube of tissue called a voxel (think of a voxel as a 3D pixel).

A full plane of voxels forms a “slice” through the brain, much like a single sheet in a stack of paper. Stacking these slices together creates a 3D volume of the brain, so you can think of the brain scan as a cube made up of many tiny cubes (voxels).

Figure 1: An illustration demonstrating the relationship between 2D digital images and 3D MRI data. On the left, a magnified view shows a 2D digital image is composed of pixels (colored squares). An arrow connects this to the right side, where multiple 2D axial slices are stacked along the Z-axis, forming a 3D volume of the brain composed of voxels (small cubes). The image is labeled to emphasize that the stacked slices create a 3D Array.

MRI data usually contains values for three spatial dimensions: X (left-right), Y (anterior-

posterior), and Z (inferior-superior). So a standard MRI scan is 3D: width, height, depth, a larger cube made of tiny cubes (voxels).

By combining these cubes in different ways, we get to see different sections of the brain. You will often see neuroscientists talk about “slices” of the brain - these are just 2D cross-sections through the 3D volume. A slice is like taking one layer out of a cake to see what’s

Less often we actually look at the entire 3d rendered brain, as we cannot look “inside” the brain that way. But in essence we have a cube of voxels representing the brain volume.

Figure 2: An illustration titled “3D MRI Volume: Voxel Brain Within a Cube (Simplified)” showing a translucent blue brain formed by numerous small voxels (3D pixels). This voxel brain is contained within a larger, transparent cube defined by a grid, emphasizing the discrete volumetric data structure.

An fMRI scan is often called “4D” because it captures three spatial dimensions (x, y, z) plus time. Each 3D brain volume is like a snapshot, and the scanner takes many of these snapshots in sequence—typically one every 2–3 seconds. When we combine these 3D volumes over time,

we get a time series: a movie of brain activity, or, in data terms, an array of cubes changing over time.

Figure 3: An illustration titled “4D MRI Data: Time Series (fMRI)” showing a horizontal sequence of four identical translucent blue brains, each composed of voxels within a transparent cube. An arrow labeled “TIME AXIS (4th Dimension)” connects the cubes, indicating the progression from “Time 1” to “Time 4” to represent a time series of 3D MRI volumes.

If you scan multiple subjects, you can imagine stacking these time series for each person, forming a “plane” of cubes—one row per subject, each row a sequence of 3D brain volumes over time.

This is a helpful way to visualize multidimensional neuroimaging data, even if the actual storage in software may differ.

Figure 4: An illustration titled “5D MRI Data: Multi-Subject Time Series” showing a vertical stack of three rows. Each row represents a different Subject (the 5th dimension) and consists of a horizontal line of four translucent blue brain cubes (composed of voxels). Arrows connect the cubes within each row, representing the progression of Time (the 4th dimension). This arrangement visualizes 5 dimensions: X, Y, Z (spatial), Time, and Subject.

So we have a cube of voxels changing over time, for multiple subjects. Each voxel is represented

as a cell in our multidimensional array. Analyzing this data without `apply()` would be a nightmare of nested loops and index juggling.

In real life, we would do lots of stuff to normalize and smooth the data to reduce the immense noise inherent in this data. MRI analyses are complex and nuanced, but let me show you how `apply()` works with this kind of structure using actual data from a BIDS (Brain Imaging Data Standard) dataset I grabbed from [OpenNeuro](#).

The data were obtained by Mueckstein (2024), and are openly available for anyone to use (with credit, of course). This dataset comes from a dual-task training study where participants performed tasks requiring either compatible (visual+manual, auditory+vocal) or incompatible (visual+vocal, auditory+manual) modality pairings. It has pre and post training sessions, though we'll only work with the pre-session data here. For our purposes, we're using the anatomical scans and a simple auditory task to demonstrate how `apply()` works with real neuroimaging data. I've reduced the data to just 10 subjects to keep things manageable.

Single subject

Let's start simple with loading in a single subject, and have a look at the MRI data.

```
library(oro.nifti)

# Path to our BIDS dataset
bids_dir <- here::here("content/blog/2025/11-01_apply/data")
```

Let's load one subject's functional run:

```
# Load a functional run for subject 01
func_file <- file.path(
  bids_dir,
  "sub-101/ses-pre/func",
  "sub-101_ses-pre_task-DT_run-01_bold.nii.gz"
)

fmri_data <- readNIfTI(func_file, reorient = FALSE)
dim(fmri_data)
```

```
[1] 64 64 37 133
```

This is a 4D array: 64 voxels in x, 64 in y, 37 in z, and 133 timepoints. That's $64 \times 64 \times 37 \times 133 = 298$ individual numbers. You definitely don't want to write nested loops for this!

One common analysis is calculating the mean activation for each voxel across time. Of course, real fMRI analysis is more complex than this, but this can illustrate how `apply()` works with 4D data. This tells you the average signal intensity at each location in the brain:

```
# Calculate mean activation across time for each voxel
# Keep x, y, z dimensions; collapse time (dimension 4)
mean_activation <- apply(
  fmri_data,
  MARGIN = c(1, 2, 3),
  FUN = mean
)
dim(mean_activation)
```

```
[1] 64 64 37
```

```
# Visualize a slice of the mean activation
image(
  mean_activation[, , 20], # Slice at z=20
  col = viridis::viridis(256),
  main = "Mean Activation - Subject 01 (Slice z=20)",
  xlab = "X-axis",
  ylab = "Y-axis"
)
```


Figure 5: Mean Activation across Voxels for Subject 01. Shows average signal intensity at each voxel location. Clear contour of a brain is visible.

We went from 4D to 3D - we collapsed the time dimension and kept the spatial dimensions. Each voxel now has one number: its average signal across the whole scan.

Similarly, we might want to know how variable the signal is at each location. High variability might indicate functional activity (or noise, depending on what you're looking for):

```
# Calculate temporal standard deviation for each voxel
temporal_sd <- apply(
  fmri_data,
  MARGIN = c(1, 2, 3),
  FUN = sd
)
```

```
# Coefficient of variation (CV) - normalized measure of variability
cv <- temporal_sd / mean_activation
```

```
# Visualize a slice of the CV
image(
  cv[, , 20], # Slice at z=20
  col = viridis::viridis(256),
  main = "Coefficient of Variation - Subject 01 (Slice z=20)",
  xlab = "X-axis",
  ylab = "Y-axis"
)
```


Figure 6: Coefficient of Variation across Voxels for Subject 01. Shows normalized variability of signal intensity at each voxel. Higher values indicate more variability relative to mean signal. Shows clear contour of a brain.

The coefficient of variation is useful because it accounts for the baseline signal intensity. A voxel with high signal and high variability has a different meaning than a voxel with low signal and high variability.

Sometimes you want to summarize across space instead of time. The “global signal” is the average intensity across all voxels at each timepoint:

```
# Subject-level summary: mean signal across all voxels over time
# Keep time dimension; collapse spatial dimensions (1, 2, 3)
global_signal <- apply(
  fmri_data,
```

```
MARGIN = 4,  
FUN = mean  
)
```

```
# Plot the global signal  
library(ggplot2)  
  
data.frame(  
  time = 1:length(global_signal),  
  signal = global_signal  
) |>  
ggplot(aes(x = time, y = signal)) +  
  geom_line(color = "steelblue", linewidth = 1.2) +  
  labs(  
    title = "Global Signal - Subject 01",  
    x = "Time (TRs)",  
    y = "Mean Signal"  
  ) +  
  theme_minimal()
```


Figure 7: Global Signal over Time for Subject 01. Shows overall mean brain signal intensity at each timepoint.

This gives you a sense of overall signal drift and scanner stability. You can see some slow drift over time, which is pretty typical in fMRI.

Multiple subjects

Now let's scale up to multiple subjects. This is where neuroimaging analysis gets computationally intensive, but `apply()` keeps it manageable:

```
fmri_files <- list.files(  
  bids_dir,  
  "ses-pre_task-DT_run-01_bold.nii.gz",
```

```

recursive = TRUE,
full.names = TRUE
)

# Extract subject IDs from filenames
subjects <- gsub(
  ".*sub-(\\d+)_ses-.*",
  "\\1",
  basename(fmri_files)
)
subjects

```

```
[1] "101" "104" "105" "108" "109" "110" "111" "113" "114" "115"
```

```

# Read in imaging files
fmri_list <- lapply(
  fmri_files,
  readNIfTI,
  reorient = FALSE
)

# Combine into 5D array: x, y, z, time, subjects
fmri_array <- array(
  unlist(fmri_list),
  dim = c(dim(fmri_list[[1]]), length(fmri_list))
)

# Add dimension names
dimnames(fmri_array) <- list(
  X = NULL,
  Y = NULL,
  Z = NULL,
  time = paste0("TR", seq_len(dim(fmri_array)[4])),
  Subject = paste0("sub-", subjects)
)

dim(fmri_array)

```

```
[1] 64 64 37 133 10
```

We now have a 5-dimensional array. Three spatial dimensions, one temporal dimension, and one subject dimension. That's over 201 million numbers to work with!

```
# tissue intensities at voxel (40,40,20) for subject 101, across all timepoints
fmri_array[40,40,20, , "sub-101"]
```

```
TR1  TR2  TR3  TR4  TR5  TR6  TR7  TR8  TR9  TR10  TR11  TR12  TR13
760  755  743  768  755  763  770  756  760  767  766  769  767
TR14  TR15  TR16  TR17  TR18  TR19  TR20  TR21  TR22  TR23  TR24  TR25  TR26
780  777  769  780  790  770  780  764  785  765  757  779  771
TR27  TR28  TR29  TR30  TR31  TR32  TR33  TR34  TR35  TR36  TR37  TR38  TR39
776  769  773  765  767  787  759  783  787  771  772  761  781
TR40  TR41  TR42  TR43  TR44  TR45  TR46  TR47  TR48  TR49  TR50  TR51  TR52
772  752  779  767  768  781  764  768  765  775  777  764  766
TR53  TR54  TR55  TR56  TR57  TR58  TR59  TR60  TR61  TR62  TR63  TR64  TR65
785  782  793  790  779  789  773  759  777  754  769  761  776
TR66  TR67  TR68  TR69  TR70  TR71  TR72  TR73  TR74  TR75  TR76  TR77  TR78
755  763  769  769  748  762  773  763  781  767  758  768  779
TR79  TR80  TR81  TR82  TR83  TR84  TR85  TR86  TR87  TR88  TR89  TR90  TR91
780  770  759  776  763  760  748  762  758  757  773  743  769
TR92  TR93  TR94  TR95  TR96  TR97  TR98  TR99  TR100  TR101  TR102  TR103  TR104
769  753  761  761  786  756  787  748  762  774  746  761  755
TR105  TR106  TR107  TR108  TR109  TR110  TR111  TR112  TR113  TR114  TR115  TR116  TR117
771  770  763  784  770  771  741  757  777  750  755  762  765
TR118  TR119  TR120  TR121  TR122  TR123  TR124  TR125  TR126  TR127  TR128  TR129  TR130
762  781  764  770  785  760  772  770  746  760  766  760  752
TR131  TR132  TR133
753  754  762
```

```
# tissue intensities at voxel (40,40,20) for all subjects, at timepoint 50
fmri_array[40,40,20, "TR50", ]
```

```
sub-101  sub-104  sub-105  sub-108  sub-109  sub-110  sub-111  sub-113  sub-114  sub-
115
       777       531       625       197       187       613       575       647       546       181
```

For group-level analysis, you might want the average across all subjects:

```
# Group-level average: mean across all subjects
# Keep x, y, z, time; collapse subjects (dimension 5)
group_average <- apply(
```

```

    fmri_array,
    MARGIN = c(1, 2, 3, 4),
    FUN = mean
  )
dim(group_average)

```

```
[1] 64 64 37 133
```

```

# visualize a slice of the group average
image(
  group_average[,,20, 50], # Slice at z=20, timepoint
  col = viridis::viridis(256),
  main = "Group Average Activation - Slice z=20, Timepoint 50",
  xlab = "X-axis",
  ylab = "Y-axis"
)

```

This gives you a 4D array representing the average response across all participants. This is your group template - what the “average brain” is doing during this task.

We can also extract summary timeseries for all subjects:

```

# Extract global signal timeseries for each subject
# Keep time and subjects; collapse spatial dimensions
subject_timeseries <- apply(
  fmri_array,
  MARGIN = c(5, 4),
  FUN = mean
)
dim(subject_timeseries)

```

```
[1] 10 133
```

This gives us a 10×133 matrix: 133 timepoints by 10 subjects. Now we can visualize all subjects together:

```

# Plot all subjects' global signals

# Convert to long format for ggplot
subject_timeseries_df <- as.data.frame(subject_timeseries) |>

```

```
tibble::rownames_to_column("subject") |>
tidyr::pivot_longer(
  cols = -subject,
  names_to = "time",
  values_to = "signal"
) |>
dplyr::mutate(time = as.numeric(gsub("TR", "", time)))

ggplot(
  subject_timeseries_df,
  aes(x = time, y = signal, color = subject)) +
  geom_line(linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  labs(
    title = "Global Signal - All Subjects",
    x = "Time (TRs)",
    y = "Mean Signal",
    color = "Subject"
  ) +
  theme_minimal()
```


Figure 8: Global Signal over Time for All Subjects. Each colored line represents a different subject's mean brain signal intensity at each timepoint.

There are some individual differences in signal patterns here. In particular, you can see there are some spikes and dips in certain subjects in the very beginning. It's always good to visually inspect your data like this before diving into more complex analyses.

The beautiful thing about `apply()` is that it scales. Whether you're working with a single subject or a hundred, whether you have 10 timepoints or 1000, the syntax stays the same. You just specify which dimensions matter for your analysis, and R handles the rest.

Wrapping up

If you work with matrices or arrays - whether that's gradebooks, experimental data, images, or brain scans - `apply()` will become one of your most-used functions. The key is understanding

the `MARGIN` parameter: it tells R which dimensions to preserve while your function collapses the rest.

Once you get comfortable with `apply()`, you'll find yourself reaching for it constantly. No more nested loops to calculate row means! No more confusing index arithmetic! Just a clear statement of what you want: "for each [row/column/slice/timepoint], calculate [thing]."

This is the power of R's array-oriented thinking. Embrace it, and your code will be cleaner, faster, and easier to understand.

Mueckstein, Kai AND Heinzl, Marie AND Gorgen. 2024. "Modality-Based Multitasking and Practice - fMRI" OpenNeuro. <https://doi.org/doi:10.18112/openneuro.ds005038.v1.0.3>.